

Smart Attendance

Software Requirement Specification

For

Smart Attendance

Version 1.0 approved

Prepared by

GROUP-4

Smart Attendance

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE

The purpose of this document is to build an application to manage the regular attendance more easily for students or employees of any institution.

1.2 DOCUMENT CONVENTIONS

This document uses the following conventions.

Database management system

SQL

1.3 INTENDED AUDIENCE AND READING SUGGESTIONS

This project is a prototype for the Smart Attendance System and it is restricted within the college premises. This project is useful for the attendance management team and as well as to the students and staffs.

1.4 PROJECT SCOPE

The purpose of the Smart Attendance System is to ease attendance management and to create a convenient, efficient application for the students and the staffs of the institution. Moreover, it will minimize the overall hardware cost and network setup.

1.5 REFERENCES

Software Engineering by Rajiv Mall

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2. OVERALL DESCRIPTION

2.1 PRODUCT PERSPECTIVE

The idea is to make a mobile application where one can give their attendance just by a single click. There will be the fingerprints of the users stored in the back-end, once the user will give their attendance, it will be authenticated in the back-end. If it matches then it will store the attendance but if not then it will show the error.

2.2 PRODUCT FUNCTIONS

The major features of Smart Attendance System as shown in below entity-relationship model (ER model)

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2.3 USER CLASS & CHARACTERISTICS

2.4 OPERATING ENVIRONMENT

Operating environment for the smart attendance system is as listed below.

- + distributed database
- + client/server system
- + Operating system: Android.
- + database: sql+ database
- + platform: Java/Kotlin

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2.5 DESIGN & IMPLEMENTATION CONSTRAINTS

1. The global schema, fragmentation schema, and allocation schema.
2. SQL commands for above queries/applications
3. How the response for application 1 and 2 will be generated. Assuming these are global queries. Explain how various fragments will be combined to do so.
4. Implement the database at least using a centralized database management system.

2.6 ASSUMPTION AND DEPENDENCIES

1. Android requirement: Nougat 7 or latest.
2. Router is configurable with our requirements (range, time in and time out)

4.EXTERNAL INTERFACE REQUIREMENTS

4.1 USER INTERFACES

- + Front-end software:Android
- + Back-end software: SQL+

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4.2 HARDWARE INTERFACES

N.A.

4.3 SOFTWARE INTERFACES

Following are the software used for the smart attendance management application.

1. Microsoft Server SQL 2012
2. Android Studio
3. Anaconda
4. Visual Studio

4.4 COMMUNICATION INTERFACES

1. LAN network
2. Wireless Routers

3. SYSTEM FEATURES

STIMULUS/RESPONSE SEQUENCES

Connect to router through android

Biometric input

Biometric verification

Biometric update

Router time out

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FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Other system features include:

DISTRIBUTED DATABASE:

Distributed database implies that a single application should be able to operate transparently on data that is spread across a variety of different databases and connected by a communication network.

CLIENT/SERVER SYSTEM

The term client/server refers primarily to an architecture or logical division of responsibilities, the client is the application (also known as the front-end), and the server is the DBMS (also known as the back-end).

A client/server system is a distributed system in which, +

Some sites are client sites and others are server sites.

- + All the data resides at the server sites.
- + All applications execute at the client sites.

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5. NONFUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

5.1 PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS

The steps involved to perform the implementation of airline database are as listed below.

A) E-R DIAGRAM

The E-R Diagram constitutes a technique for representing the logical structure of a database in a pictorial manner. This analysis is then used to organize data as a relation, normalizing relation and finally obtaining a relation database.

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- ✦ **ENTITIES:** Which specify distinct real-world items in an application.
- ✦ **PROPERTIES/ATTRIBUTES:** Which specify properties of an entity and relationships.
- ✦ **RELATIONSHIPS:** Which connect entities and represent meaningful dependencies between them.

B) NORMALIZATION:

The basic objective of normalization is to reduce redundancy which means that information is to be stored only once. Storing information several times leads to wastage of storage space and increase in the total size of the data stored.

If a database is not properly designed it can give rise to modification anomalies. Modification anomalies arise when data is added to, changed or deleted from a database table. Similarly, in traditional databases as well as improperly designed relational databases, data redundancy can be a problem. These can be eliminated by normalizing a database.

Normalization is the process of breaking down a table into smaller tables. So that each table deals with a single theme. There are three different kinds of modifications of anomalies and formulated the first, second and third normal forms (3NF) is considered sufficient for most practical purposes. It should be considered only after a thorough analysis and complete understanding of its implications.

5.2 SAFETY REQUIREMENTS

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If there is extensive damage to a wide portion of the database due to catastrophic failure, such as a disk crash, the recovery method restores a past copy of the database that was backed up to archival storage (typically tape) and reconstructs a more current state by reapplying or redoing the operations of committed transactions from the backed up log, up to the time of failure.

5.3 SECURITY REQUIREMENTS

Security systems need database storage just like many other applications. However, the special requirements of the security market mean that vendors must choose their database partner carefully.

5.4 SOFTWARE QUALITY ATTRIBUTES

- + **AVAILABILITY:** all time power supply
- + **CORRECTNESS:** can be modified on client request

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- ✦ **MAINTAINABILITY:** The administrators should have the correct database stored.
- ✦ **USABILITY:** This should satisfy a maximum number of customers needs.

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